

AGRICULTURAL INPUT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: Previous studies have established a substantial connection between agricultural and economic growth because of agricultural growth's ability to attract foreign investment, enhance employment rates, alleviate hunger, and promote economic development. This study has made a unique contribution by examining the link between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria while considering factors such as foreign direct investment (FDI), gross national income (GNI), and inflation rate. The secondary data used in this study were collected from the World Bank development indicator from 1990 to 2022. The unit root test was applied, and the results show that the series are integrated of order 1, which eliminated the presence of unit roots that could cause erroneous findings. The Johansen co-integration shows a long-term association between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the fitted OLS regression model indicates that agricultural input, foreign direct investment (FDI), and gross national income (GNI) have a positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth, whereas the inflation rate hinders the nation's economic growth. Thus, in response to the increasing inflation rate, it is imperative for the government to allocate significant investments toward the agricultural sector. This will lead to an increase in agricultural output, thereby promoting economic growth.

Keywords: Agricultural input, Economic growth, Unit root, Johansen Cointegration, OLS regression model.

1. Introduction

Every nation worldwide has consistently pursued the goal of attaining swift and consistent economic growth and development (World Bank, 2022). This can only be accomplished with the direct involvement of agriculture, especially in developing economies. Hence, the correlation between agricultural input and economic growth is of utmost importance.

The agricultural industry in Nigeria played a crucial role in driving economic growth before the discovery of oil in 1956 at Olaibiri in the Niger Delta, following fifty years of exploration. Agriculture is a significant sector in the Nigerian economy, with over 70% of the total population involved in it, especially in rural and suburban areas. The agricultural sector contributes approximately 24% of the gross domestic product (GDP) (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Agricultural input as a contribution to Nigeria's GDP (Source: World Bank)

Nigeria possesses a remarkably varied agro-ecological state, enabling the cultivation of a diverse array of agricultural commodities. Therefore, agriculture is a crucial component of the economy. The sector holds significant importance in terms of its capacity to generate employment and its contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) and export revenue earnings. The gross domestic product (GDP) increased by 1.9% in 2018, compared with a growth rate of 0.8% in 2017, as calculated at constant basic prices. The non-oil sectors, which saw a 2.0% increase, were primarily responsible for the gain. In contrast, oil sector output grew by 1.1%. The services, agricultural, manufacturing, and construction sectors contributed 1.1%, 0.5%, 0.3%, and 0.1%, respectively, to the growth of the gross domestic product (GDP). Conversely, the trade sector made a negative contribution of -0.1% to GDP growth (CBN, 2018). The agricultural sector, along with the services sector, played a significant role in the recent growth of the Nigerian economy. The growth in agricultural output can be attributed to the successful implementation of the Anchor Borrowers' Programme and increased infrastructural spending resulting from the implementation of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan.

During the oil boom period in Nigeria from 1973 to 1983, there was a disregard for the agricultural sector and a greater focus on the oil sector. Foreign exchange earnings experienced a significant surge, leading to a transformation of the Nigerian economy from a land-based to a water-based economy. This shift occurred when the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) was introduced in 1986, with the backing of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank. Because of SAP, there were reforms in agricultural and business

regulations, trade policies, and foreign exchange systems. Odetola and Etunmu (2013) stated that the significance of agriculture to the Nigerian economy is obvious due to the country's abundant production elements, including vast arable land, water, human resources, suitable weather and climate, and capital. Therefore, attaining economic growth in Nigeria will be exceedingly challenging until the sector is developed. The most expeditious method to boost economic growth is to exploit the nation's production advantage in this sector.

In addition, the world economy has significantly declined because of inflation, particularly in developing nations such as Nigeria (Al Marhubi, 2021). Thus, it is imperative that the government invest extensively in agriculture to diversify the economy. Exports will increase as a result, drawing in foreign capital and increasing returns on foreign direct investment (FDI). Furthermore, as favorable agricultural inputs are anticipated to have a favorable influence on FDI and enhance economic growth, investing in agriculture will help mitigate the negative effects of political instability in the nation because of insecurity on the economy that has disrupted agricultural activities (World Bank, 2022; Alfaro & Chauvin, 2020).

Hence, the primary aim of this paper is to empirically investigate the link between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria while considering factors such as foreign direct investment return, inflation rate, and gross national income (GNI). This will be done using the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model and other suitable econometric approaches that previous studies have overlooked. The findings of this study will significantly contribute to the current body of knowledge.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Nigeria's significance is further underscored by the fact that it is one of the biggest nations in Africa, with a projected population of 226.2 million in 2023 (Statista, 2023). The entire nation is located in a tropical region, particularly on Africa's western coast near the Gulf of Guinea. Nigeria's varied agro-ecological state makes it possible to cultivate a large variety of agricultural products. Consequently, agriculture is essential to the economy. The industry holds great significance because of its ability to create job opportunities and its substantial impact on GDP and export revenue. A major sector of the economy, agriculture offers significant opportunities for employment development, ensures food security, and reduces poverty. However, over time, these untapped potentials have played a significant role in the agriculture sector's declining productivity in both domestic and international trade. With a 42% market share in 1961, Nigeria was the world's top exporter of groundnuts. In addition, the nation exported 27% of the world's palm oil and 18% of cocoa and continued to lead West Africa in cotton exports with a 1.4% share. More than 60% of the population is employed in agriculture, which generates more than 40% of the nation's GDP (UNCTAD, 2018).

In its literal sense, economic growth is the expansion of an economy in terms of size without necessarily indicating an improvement in the overall quality of the economy. Economic growth is defined by Singh (2017) as the rise in both the production and consumption of commodities and services. Gross domestic product (GDP) growth serves as a gage. The result of humans using resources efficiently and reorganizing them to increase their value is economic growth. For an economy to expand, its natural resources—minerals, water, land, and energy—must be increased. The economy depletes its natural resources when it grows rapidly or becomes numerous. The Nigerian economy has grown significantly thanks in large part to the country's agriculture sector. A crucial sector of the economy, agriculture ensures food security, reduces poverty, and offers significant employment opportunities. However, these potentials have mostly remained unrealized, which has led to a decline in the performance of the agriculture sector over time in both local and international trade. With a 42% market share in

1961, Nigeria was the top groundnut exporter in the world. Additionally, the nation held a significant share of global palm oil exports, amounting to 27%. In addition, with an 18% market share, it held a prominent role in the cocoa sector. Besides, it contributed 1.4% of the global cotton trade and was a major exporter of cotton to West Africa (FMARD, 2011).

In Nigeria, the industrial sector accounted for 39.21% of the country's total economic growth in 2012. Its contribution increased significantly by 41.93% in the third quarter of 2013. This is explained by the fact that agricultural production increased steadily in 2013. Compared with a growth rate of 5.68% in the same quarter in 2011, the industry experienced a 3.83% increase in growth in the fourth quarter of 2012. In comparison to the 3.89% growth rate recorded during the same period in 2012, the output showed a 5.08% growth rate in the third quarter of 2013. Moreover, it was higher than the 4.52% recorded in the second quarter of 2013. However, compared to sectors such as education and financial intermediation, the rate of job growth remained relatively low (NBS, 2020).

Numerous empirical studies on the connection between agriculture and economic growth have been conducted because the agricultural sector is crucial to economic growth, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria. Additionally, Ijirshar (2015) conducted a study that specifically examined the relationship between agricultural exports and economic growth from 1970 to 2012. The results of the co-integration test demonstrate that real GDP, real exchange rate, real agricultural input, trade openness index, and inflation have a consistent relationship. The Nigerian economy has benefited from agricultural inputs, as demonstrated by the error-correcting approach.

According to Odetola and Etunmu (2013), Nigeria's agriculture industry played a significant part in the country's economy as it continuously and favorably contributed to economic growth between 1960 and 2011. The presence of a causal relationship between GDP growth and agricultural expansion was confirmed using the Granger causality test. More specifically, it was shown that rising agricultural productivity correlated with rising GDP, whereas falling agricultural productivity correlated with declining GDP. Therefore, the following is how we may develop a research hypothesis regarding the connection between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria:

H1: Agricultural inputs have a positive contribution to Nigeria's economic growth.

3. Research Methodology

This study adopts a causal research design, and the secondary data were collected annually from 1990 to 2022 via the World Bank Development Indicator on the basis of considering the current period as well as the availability of the dataset using purposive sampling. The methods of analysis adopted are summary statistics (like the mean and standard deviation) and empirical analysis such as the OLS regression model, unit root test, and Johansen co-integration test. Meanwhile, diagnostic tests such as multicollinearity, normality test, autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and model stability were also conducted to determine the validity and robustness of the fitted empirical model.

According to Adebajo (2022), OLS regression helps establish a linear link between the dependent and independent variables. It also helps to examine the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The unit root test is necessary to ensure that the unit root is eliminated among the series or the variables of interest to eliminate an erroneous conclusion, while the co-integration test using the Johansen method helps to establish if there is a co-integration among the series. Therefore, it is important to functionally specify the empirical model applied in this study as follows:

$$\text{Economic growth} = (\text{Agricultural input, FDI, GNI, Inflation}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Economic growth is proxied by gross domestic product (GDP), which is the dependent variable; agricultural input (AI) is the main independent variable, which is checked by FDI; and other variables such as gross national income (GNI) and inflation are control variables.

Meanwhile, we can specify the empirical model mathematically by introducing log to the dependent variable (Kissel & Poserina, 2017) to enhance the significance of the predictor variables and the model performance. The model can be written as follows:

$$\ln\text{GDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AI}_t + \beta_2\text{FDI}_t + \beta_3\text{GNI}_t + \beta_4\text{Inflation}_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where β_0 is the constant term, β_1 to β_4 are the slopes or coefficient estimates of the predictor variables, μ is the stochastic error term, and t is the period in years.

Table 1: Variable measurements

Variables	Measurement
GDP	Billions of USD
Agricultural Input	% of GDP
FDI	Billions of USD
GNI	Billions of USD
Inflation	Percentage (%)

Source: World Bank

4. Results and discussion

Table 2: Summary statistics

Statistics	lnGDP	AGRIC.INPUT	FDI	GNI	INFLATION
Mean	5.096598	24.28299	2.985887	234.4007	18.08466
Median	5.474180	23.89370	2.005354	192.5165	12.87660
Maximum	6.352950	36.96508	8.841062	533.5136	72.83550
Minimum	3.323315	19.99025	-0.18679	32.78878	5.388000
Std. Dev.	1.013786	3.710512	2.627407	182.4653	16.10793
Observations	33	33	33	33	33

Source: Author's computation using EViews software

Table 2 shows that the average log of the GDP is approximately 5.1 billion USD with a variability of approximately 1 billion USD during the period under review; the average agricultural input is approximately 24% of the GDP with a variability of approximately 4% of the GDP; the average foreign direct investment (FDI) is approximately 2.99 billion USD with a variability of approximately 2.63 billion USD; the average gross national income (GNI) is approximately 234 billion USD with a variability of approximately 182 billion USD; and the average inflation rate is approximately 18% with a variability of approximately 16% during the period under review, which is from 1990 to 2022.

Table 3: Unit root test

D(lnGDP)	t-Statistic	P-value
Augmented Dickey– Fuller test statistic	-4.393267	0.0016
D(Agricultural Input)		
Augmented Dickey– Fuller test statistic	-6.425643	0.0000
D(FDI)		
Augmented Dickey– Fuller test statistic	-5.975807	0.0000
D(GNI)		
Augmented Dickey– Fuller test statistic	-3.266784	0.0257
D(Inflation)		
Augmented Dickey– Fuller test statistic	-4.301429	0.0021

Source: Author’s computation using E-Views software

Table 3 shows that the series such as the log of GDP, agricultural input, FDI, GNI, and inflation become stationary after the first difference, that is, they are integrated of order 1 ($P < .05$), indicating that the presence of unit root that could cause erroneous findings has been eliminated. This suggests that further empirical analysis can be carried out.

Table 4: Johansen co-integration

Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.713027	86.89741	69.81889	0.0012
At most 1 *	0.626788	48.19808	47.85613	0.0464
At most 2	0.327549	17.64423	29.79707	0.5924
At most 3	0.125681	5.342620	15.49471	0.7714
At most 4	0.037318	1.178995	3.841466	0.2776

Trace test indicates 2 co-integrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

Source: Author’s computation using EViews software

Table 4 shows that two of the co-integrating factors, None* and At Most 1*, are statistically significant at the 5% level (i.e., $P < .05$), indicating the presence of co-integration among the series, which indicates a long-term association between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria while accounting for foreign direct investment returns, gross national income, and inflation rate.

Table 5: OLS regression model

OLS regression					
lnGDP	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	VIF
C	3.350361	0.344621	9.721865	0.0000	NA
AGRICULTURAL INPUT	0.025148	0.012104	2.077618	0.0470	1.338797
FDI	0.057436	0.017191	3.341073	0.0024	1.353961
GNI	0.00481	0.000292	16.49031	0.0000	1.880327
INFLATION	-0.009042	0.002692	-3.359219	0.0023	1.247554
R-squared	0.95895				
Adjusted R-squared	0.953086				
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000				

Source: Author’s computation using EViews software

Table 5 shows that the coefficient of agricultural input has a significant positive effect on economic growth ($P < .05$), supporting the research hypothesis that agricultural input has a positive contribution to Nigerian economic growth, indicating that a high level of agricultural input contributes to greater economic growth in Nigeria. Table 5 also reveals that coefficient estimates of FDI and GNI have a significant positive impact on economic growth ($P < .01$), indicating that a high level of FDI and GNI will contribute to higher economic growth in Nigeria, while the coefficient of the inflation rate has a significant negative influence on economic growth ($P < .01$), indicating that a high inflation rate results in a decline in economic growth, which agrees with the current economic situation in Nigeria. The overall OLS regression model ($P < .01$) is statistically significant, indicating a significant linear relationship between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria while accounting for FDI, GNI, and inflation. The R-squared value of 0.959 indicates that 95.9% of the variation in economic growth in Nigeria can be explained by agricultural input, FDI, GNI, and the inflation rate, while the remaining 4.1% can be attributed to other factors not included in the model. Additionally, the variance inflation factor (VIF) of all the predictor variables is less than 5, indicating that the model does not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity, and this also means that the estimated results of the model are not misleading. The overall model is statistically significant, and the R-squared value is relatively large, indicating that the fitted OLS regression model is sufficiently adequate.

Table 6: Diagnostic tests

Heteroskedasticity Test:	Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey	F-statistic	Prob. F(4,28)	0.891
		1.251482	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.8696
		0.459809	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.9773

Breusch– Godfrey Serial Correlation

LM Test:

F-statistic	4.601962	Prob. F(2,26)	0.0195
Obs*R-squared	8.627717	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0134

Source: Author’s computation using EViews software

Table 6 shows the diagnostic and assumption tests such as the heteroscedasticity test ($P > .05$) and the serial correlation test ($P > .01$), which means that we do not reject the null hypothesis, and this suggests that the fitted OLS model does not suffer from the problems of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation.

In addition, Figure 2 displays the histogram plot for the normality test using the Jarque– Bera test ($P > 0.05$), showing that the residuals are normally distributed, which agrees with the assumption of normality in the ordinary least squares (OLS) model. Figure 3 displays the CUSUM test for model stability. The model falls within the two 95% confidence intervals, which means that the parameters of the fitted OLS model are stable.

Figure 2: Normality test

Figure 3: CUSUM test

4.1 Discussion of the findings

The analysis conducted in this study reveals that Table 3 demonstrates that the series, including the logarithm of GDP, agricultural input, FDI, GNI, and inflation, exhibit stationarity after the first difference. This indicates that these variables are integrated of order 1, implying that the presence of a unit root, which could lead to inaccurate findings, has been eliminated. Consequently, this suggests that additional empirical analysis can be conducted. Table 4 demonstrates that two of the co-integrating equations exhibit statistical significance at the 5% level, suggesting the existence of co-integration among the series. This indicates a long-term connection between agricultural inputs and economic growth in Nigeria, considering factors such as foreign direct investment returns, gross national income, and inflation rate. These findings support the research conducted by Ijirshar (2015), which also concludes that agricultural input and economic growth have a long-term relationship.

Table 5 demonstrates that the coefficient of agricultural input has a substantial and positive impact on economic growth. This supports the research hypothesis that agricultural inputs play a constructive role in the economic growth of Nigeria. This suggests that a higher level of agricultural input leads to greater economic growth in the country. This finding is consistent with the findings of Odetola and Etunmu (2013), who discovered a positive correlation between increasing agricultural productivity and GDP growth. Table 5 demonstrates that the estimated coefficients for FDI and GNI have a statistically significant positive effect on economic growth. This suggests that a greater amount of FDI and GNI will lead to increased economic growth in Nigeria. On the other hand, the coefficient for the inflation rate has a statistically significant negative impact on economic growth. This implies that a higher inflation rate is associated with a decrease in economic growth, which aligns with the current economic situation in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion and policy implications

Prior research has established a substantial correlation between agricultural and economic growth because of agricultural growth's ability to attract foreign investment, enhance employment rates, alleviate hunger, and promote economic development. This study has made a unique contribution by examining the relationship between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria, while taking into account factors such as foreign direct investment (FDI), gross national income (GNI), and inflation rate. Previous studies have overlooked these variables. The analysis reveals that agricultural input, foreign direct investment (FDI), and gross national income (GNI) have a positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth, whereas the inflation rate hinders the nation's economic growth.

Thus, in response to the increasing inflation rate, it is imperative for the government to allocate significant investments toward the agricultural sector. This will lead to an increase in agricultural output, thereby promoting economic growth. Additionally, it is crucial to establish robust security measures to counteract banditry and terrorist activities that pose a threat to agricultural operations. Furthermore, the implementation of a consistent and effective economic policy that prioritizes agriculture will attract foreign investors, reduce inflation, and optimize Nigeria's economic growth.

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